

21ST CENTURY AND DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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***Annotation:** Uzbek linguistics is distinguished by its own characteristics. This article analyzes Uzbek linguistics of the period of independence and the 21st century.*

***Keywords:** bourgeois science, component, formal-functional, anthropocentric interpretation, method.*

INTRODUCTION

This year marks a quarter of a century since the independence of our republic. Although this is a short period of time for history, during this period huge changes took place in the economic, political, cultural and educational life of our country. Our national values and spiritual traditions were forgotten because the former Soviet system pursued the absurd policy of uniting nations into a single socialist nation for 70 years. By the years of independence, there was an opportunity to popularize the rich cultural and spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, to determine their place in the world civilization. In this place, the significant creative works carried out in the field of studying the rich scientific and artistic heritage of great scholars such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abduhaliq Gijduvani, Imam al Bukhari, Mahmud Koshgari, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Muhammad Reza Aghahi it is enough to bring it before our eyes. By this time, the psychology of muteness and dependence, which had been ingrained in our minds for centuries, was gradually replaced by the psychology of freedom, creativity, and self-sacrifice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

By the years of independence, the harmful tradition of studying the phonetic, grammatical and lexical system of our language based on the models of Russian linguistics, which prevailed during the former Soviet period, was abandoned. In the 20th century, getting rid of the chain of Marxist teachings, which had become the only science methodology, and the opportunity to freely use the best philosophical teachings in the scientific knowledge of the world and language system led to further strengthening of the scientific-theoretical foundations of our country's linguistics [2]. As a result, structural-systemic linguistics, which was declared as a "bourgeois science" and a "science alien to Marxist methodology" during the former Soviet period, and its methods of checking language units were widely used in the framework of Uzbek linguistics with the honor of independence [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Uzbek linguistics, special attention is being paid to the in-depth study of general and private scientific research methodology and methods, their inculcation in the minds of young researchers. In this place, the well-known philosopher and scientist, prof. N. Shermuhamedova's "Philosophical issues of sciences" (Tashkent, "University", 2005), "Language construction: analysis methods and methodology" by T. Bushuy, Sh. Safarov (Tashkent, "Fan", 2007), prof. It should be noted that important scientific researches such as A. Nurmonov's "Linguistic Research Methodology and Methods" (Tashkent, "Akademnashr", 2012), Sh. Safarov's "Language Theory and Linguistic Methodology" (2015) have been published.

If before independence, Uzbek linguistics was mainly engaged in the study of the phonetic and grammatical structure of the Uzbek language on a simple descriptive basis, by the years of independence, attention was paid to solving the problems of general theoretical linguistics on the basis of the materials of the Uzbek language, to clarifying the issues of the theory of linguistics and the history of linguistic teachings. By this time, textbooks and manuals devoted to the theory of linguistics by scientists such as A. Abduazizov, R. Rasulov, N. Turniyozov, B. Orinboev, M. Iriskulov, A.

Nurmonov, Sh. Iskandarov, as well as A. Nurmonov, B. Orinboev. The works of scholars such as Jabbarov on the history of Uzbek linguistics have appeared. It is only because of independence that Uzbek linguistics has a long history, that Uzbek linguists founded a number of directions such as comparative-historical linguistics, contrastive linguistics, creating ideographic dictionaries long before some European linguists, and it has become a tradition to illuminate the content of lexemes based on component analysis. Under the circumstances, there was an opportunity to clarify and convey to the scientific community that this method was widely used by Uzbek linguists in the 15th century [4].

Before independence, theoretical issues of linguistics were mainly studied by Russian linguists, and linguists from the allied countries followed them and applied their scientific views to concrete national languages. By the years of independence, Uzbek linguists boldly started solving theoretical problems. In particular, a number of researches were conducted to solve the controversial issues related to the basic building units of the language, such as the systematic nature of the language, structure, phoneme, morpheme, lexeme, word, phrase, sentence devices, and text. At this point, it is enough to recall academician A. Hojiev's twenty scientific articles on the current issues of Uzbek linguistics, and the large monographic study created on this basis [5]. Or, it should be noted that two scientific studies on the theoretical problems of the syntax of word combinations have been published: A. Madaminov's "Theoretical problems of the syntax of word combinations" (2013), S. Nazarova's "Syntax of word combinations in substantial interpretation" (2015) are among them.

It is well known that no language can be fully studied without being separated from the person who is the —language owner|. Because in the process of every speech communication, the desire of the speaker, his attitude to reality, and the skill of using language units are noticeable. In connection with the study of these problems, the direction of anthropo-linguistics was born in linguistics. Accordingly, the formation of anthropo-linguistics is considered by world linguists as a new era of linguistics. Anthropo-linguistics includes a number of directions, such as linguistic

semantics, pragmatic linguistics, cognitive linguistics, and neurolinguistics, which study the internal structure of language in relation to the speaker and listener. It is noteworthy that in the years of independence, a number of scientific researches were carried out in Uzbek linguistics in the field of anthropolinguistics. It is worth noting the interesting research conducted by scientists such as N. Mahmudov in linguistic semantics, M. Hakimov, Sh. Safarov in the fields of pragmatic linguistics and cognitive linguistics. Especially prof. A. Nurmonov and prof. A. Rahimov's "Introduction to Linguosynergetics" (2013), Prof. Sh. Safarov's "Cognitive Linguistics" (2006), "Pragmalinguistics" (2008), "Semantics" (2013), "Language Theory and Linguistic Methodology" (2015), prof. "Semasiology of the Uzbek language" (2010), "Phonetics of the Uzbek language" (2013), prof. "Anthroponymics of the Uzbek language" by E. Begmatov (2013), prof. "Fundamentals of Uzbek pragmalinguistics" by M. Hakimov (2013), prof. N. Husanov's large monographic research entitled "History of Uzbek anthroponyms" (2014) was a great achievement of Uzbek linguistics in the years of independence.

In the years of independence, the rapid development of information technologies in our country, in turn, prepared a solid foundation for the formation of the field of computer linguistics. In the following years, the works of scientists such as A.Polatov, B.Yoldoshev, A.Rahimov dedicated to computer linguistics were published [6]. This serves to enrich Uzbek linguistics with a new direction.

In the years of independence, the training of linguists according to world standards is also given special importance in our country. During this period, young scientific researchers with a very bright future appeared who could easily communicate in foreign languages, who could freely use the scientific achievements achieved in the most developed countries of the world through the language of this country, and who could introduce Uzbek science to the world. For example, J. Eltazarov, doctor of philology, worked as a professor at the universities of countries such as Germany, France, Japan, Korea, and Turkey, and gave lectures on the problems of Altaic studies. Many more such examples can be given.

With the achievement of independence, serious attention was paid to the fundamental reform of the education system in our country. In our country, several variants of textbooks have been created for all stages of education from the mother tongue. In the selection of such textbooks, the —Mother Tongue‖ textbooks for the 5th, 6th, 7th, and 9th grades were compiled by the group of authors headed by N. Mahmudov, the —Mother Tongue‖ textbook for the 8th grade, which was compiled under the guidance of M. Kadirov, and the academician A. Nurmonov The three-volume "Modern Uzbek Literary Language" textbook for lyceums, the "Uzbek Language and Literature" textbook for vocational colleges under the leadership of A.Rafiev was recognized as the winner and has been published several times to date. At the same time, more than ten types of different educational dictionaries have been published in our country, and they are widely used in the educational process [1]. The publication of an encyclopedic dictionary called "Mother Tongue" for schoolchildren was also an important event in Uzbek language didactics [2]. For the philology faculties of higher education, —Current Literary Uzbek Language‖ (2006; 2010) was published by the team of authors under the leadership of Sh.Rakhmatullaev, M.Mirtojiev, and R.Saifullaeva.

Textbooks such as "Current Uzbek language" (2007), "Modern Uzbek language" (Morfology, 2008; Syntax, 2010) were created.

It is known that linguistics and poetics are related to each other and deal with the analysis of artistic text as two branches growing from the same vein. During the years of independence, prof. A number of researchers such as I. Mirzaev, M. Yoldoshev, M. Yaqubbekova, G. Muhammadjonova, D. Nematova, L. Jalolova, A. Hasanov have carried out effective work. Especially M. Yoldoshev's —Basics of literary text and its linguopoetic analysis‖ (2007), —Linguopoetics of literary text‖ (2008), —Linguistic analysis of literary text‖ (2009), S. Boymirzaeva's —Literary text and compound sentence‖ (2008), Monographic studies such as "Semantics of temporality in text content" (2009), "Text modality" (2010), "Issues of the language of works of art" (2016) by B.Yoldoshev are distinguished by their scientific-

theoretical depth, logical consistency, and harmony of theoretical ideas with practice. D. Khudoyberganova's monograph entitled "Anthropocentric study of the text" (2013) and the doctoral dissertation on the topic "Anthropocentric interpretation of artistic texts in the Uzbek language" defended on this basis (2015) initiated a more in-depth study of the problems of text linguistics in Uzbek linguistics. Similarly, A. Mamajonov and M. Abdupattoev's work entitled "Text theory" (2016) is of great importance in the detailed study of methodological and semantic features of text types.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the last twenty-five years, Uzbek linguistics has achieved significant achievements in the field of scientific in-depth study of all units of the Uzbek language, taking into account its internal features. Serious attention was paid to the standardization of official and scientific methods, which had become very weak during the Soviet period. The task now is to create a linguo-areal atlas of the local dialects of the Uzbek language, to create a textbook for the philology faculties of higher educational institutions, which takes into account the latest achievements of Uzbek linguistics, fully meets the requirements of the textbook in terms of scientific and methodological aspects, reflects the spirit of independence, and is acceptable to everyone. , phonopoetics, morphopoetics, and syntaxpoetics are serious issues. We think that Uzbek linguists will fulfill such tasks without deviation and will become real propagandists of the free language policy carried out in our country due to independence.

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